

THE FORMATION OF THE THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF NATURE INTRODUCTION AS A SCIENCE

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Abstract: This article provides information on how the theory and methodology of nature introduction was formed as a science and how this science is important as other specialized sciences. Because nature is our greatest wealth.

Keywords: Vernadsky, nature, the book "Avesta", methodology, Abu Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi, ecological relations, Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan Al-Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, environment.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that nature is an invaluable value for humanity. Nature is the place of birth, life, growth, and activity. Man lives, grows, and develops together with nature. Humanity not only affects nature, but also directly depends on it. Factors related to nature also determine technical, economic, and ecological relations. This situation requires the need to coordinate people's relations with nature and the environment. Instilling love for the animal world in children from an early age, protecting inanimate and living nature is a problem that should be studied as one of the initial elements of ecological education. In particular, this area has not been studied specifically, and today the need for a well-rounded person by the state and society is increasing.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the current conditions of globalization, increasing competition requires the development and implementation of completely new approaches and principles for the more sustainable and rapid development of our country. In particular, the

biosphere has been developing for long historical periods, since the emergence of life on Earth. The part of the Earth where living organisms and biogenic sedimentary rocks are distributed was called the biosphere by the Russian scientist Academician V.I. Vernadsky (from Greek - “bios” - life, “sphere” - sphere). The biosphere is considered the “shell of life” of our planet and forms a complex set of eco-cisterns consisting of close communication and relationships of living organisms. Ecological problems are universal, because the biosphere does not recognize state borders. Common human problems also give rise to universal tasks. In today's era of globalization, solving ecological problems is relevant. Reliance on historical scientific sources helps to reveal the fundamental essence of science. The first step towards introducing the term “ecology” into science was taken by the German scientist Ernst Haeckel. Today, the relationship of man to the external environment is fundamentally different from that of other living organisms. In 1921, a new science called “Human Ecology” was introduced by American scientists Borta and Park. The teachings that it is the duty of man to preserve and cherish nature found expression in the teachings of great scientists who came from Turanian Turkestan. Scientists wrote down rich information about the use of nature in their time, the events and phenomena associated with them. They expressed in their works the need to cultivate love for nature and high morality. Our most reliable, ancient manuscript “Avesta” is considered the invaluable property of our people. This rare book is the spiritual and historical heritage of our ancestors who lived on this land thirty centuries ago, which we have left to our descendants.

"Avesta" is a historical document testifying to the great state, high spirituality and culture of this ancient land at that time. "Avesta" is a philosophy that harmonizes the relationship between nature, society and man through spiritual, spiritual and moral criteria, and encourages people to study the world around them. "Avesta" contains valuable information about unique medicinal herbs. In addition, recommendations are given on housing, environment, nature protection, and its

preservation. "Avesta" writes about keeping the earth, water, room, human body parts, and clothes clean. People who polluted the environment, streets, bushes, meadows, and land were punished. Also. In order to maintain environmental cleanliness and prevent diseases, it was ordered to bury garbage and contaminated areas with stones, soil, and sand. The work also shows ways to eliminate disease-spreading insects, as well as properly care for domestic animals. Among the scientists who lived and worked in Central Asia in the Middle Ages, Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Al-Farghani and others made a great contribution to the development of natural science. At a time when ecology had not yet emerged, they expressed valuable ideas about nature and its balance, the world of plants and animals, and respect for nature. The great scholar Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi (783-850) wrote in one of his treatises: "Know that when the eyes of a river shed tears, sorrow and trouble have befallen it. People, do not withhold your love from the river!" What did Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi mean when he said the "tears of the eyes" of a river? Perhaps he meant excessive waste of river water? However, our great grandfather, first of all, meant that people and the river "understand each other" and develop mutual love. In 847, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi wrote a work called "Kitab surat al-arz". It contains information about the world's oceans, land continents, poles, equators, deserts, mountains, rivers and seas, lakes and forests, their flora and fauna, as well as the main wealth of the earth and other natural resources. Abu Nasr al-Farabi. The scientific and philosophical heritage of Abu Nasr al-Farabi (873-950 AD), one of the largest and most famous representatives of the socio-philosophical thoughts of the peoples of Central Asia, is extremely rich. His works have not yet been fully deciphered. The German scientist M.K. Brockelmann lists 180 works by Farabi in various fields. His works on natural science, such as "The Structure of Human Organs" and "On Animal Organs and Their Functions," also focus on the structure, properties, and functions of certain organs in humans and

animals. Al-Farabi distinguished between natural and man-made things. He also considered that natural things were created by nature and that the influence of the factor was great in this, and that natural and artificial selection and other influences on nature were comprehensively evaluated. Thus, “The essence of man is known in reason, and the essence of reason is known in action.” Abu Rayhan Al-Biruni (973-1048 AD) tried to explain the phenomena in the universe by the laws of development, the interaction of things and phenomena. The scientist explained some phenomena on Earth through the influence of the sun. Al-Biruni’s scientific views were mainly reflected in his works “Saydana”, “Mineralogy”, and “Monuments of Ancient Generations”.

Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037 AD) is known as a great encyclopedist. He wrote 450 works, 240 of which have survived to our time. Among the works of Ibn Sina, the masterpiece "The Canon of Medicine" is an encyclopedia of medical science and is considered the pinnacle of the spread of medieval medical science. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483-1530). Babur was not only a poet, but also a king, hunter, historian, gardener and naturalist. In the work "Baburnama", Babur described the nature, wealth, customs, animals and plants of the places he visited. The work contains many folk sayings related to land, water and air. In his work, Babur described the geographical location of the place, the climate it belongs to, its plants and animals, and noted that since ancient times in Central Asia there have been melons, wheat, apricots, pears and several varieties of fruits. In the work, Babur compared the nature and specific features of the places he visited with Andijan, and described in detail the animal world of Central Asia, Afghanistan, Khorasan and India. It is impossible to properly educate the younger generation in nature without knowing the goals and tasks of education. For this, it is appropriate to recall how the idea of \u200b\u200bthe goals of education reflecting the interests of the people arose, how these ideas later developed, and what definition and description were given from the pedagogical side. It should be said that the

emergence of each science in life is the result of vital necessity. The methodology for introducing children to nature is also the product of such vital necessity. This science sets itself the goal of educating young people through these elements of nature. Education is the main task of pedagogy. In history, the views of such scientists as the famous philosophers of ancient Greece Plato and Aristotle, and the Italian pedagogue Mark, were of particular importance in forming the foundations of pedagogical theory. However, the education of young people through the elements of nature began, first of all, with the history of progressive pedagogues in the West.

CONCLUSION

One of the Western pedagogues who initiated the development of scientific pedagogy and paid great attention to the education of children of preschool age was Jan Amos Komensky. The famous Czech pedagogue J.A. Komensky is considered the founder of democratic pedagogy in the history of mankind. In his opinion, man is the most beautiful creature of nature.

Man can learn everything by following nature. Y.A. Komensky recommended learning 18 subjects in his "School of Mothers." In his opinion, a six-year-old child should know: water, earth, air, fire, rain, snow, ice, stone, iron, trees, grass, birds, fish, etc.; the difference between light and darkness, knowledge about the sky, sun, moon, stars, their daily rising and setting; what a mountain, valley, field, river, village, city are, depending on the nature of the place where he lives. Y.A. Komensky explained everything by linking it to nature. To attract the attention of readers, he gave interesting titles to the books and fully expressed their content. He said that the most beautiful thing in this field is to take a sample from the various landscapes of the garden. Komensky approached the issues of theoretical knowledge as a materialist. He was the first to put forward the idea of harmonizing education with nature, that is, to base education on nature and its general laws. Comenius's special work on the education of children of preschool age, "The School

of Mothers," became the world's first program and manual for preschool education. His recommendations in the field of cultivating the desire for activity, love of labor, love of nature, honesty, cleanliness, politeness and other such qualities are very valuable. The theory created by Y. A. Comenius almost three and a half centuries ago was the first step in educating young people and introducing them to nature. I.G. Pestalozzi (1746-1827) - Born into a Swiss doctor's family. A well-known pedagogue-democrat, preschool educator I.G. Pestalozzi created the basis of a special methodology for preschool education. In it, he justified the content of elementary education in natural sciences, arithmetic, and local history, and recommended that geography and medical sciences be integrated to enrich the child's language. K.D. Ushinsky, in addition to justifying the content of education in primary schools, also developed its laws, rules, procedures, methods and tools, making a great contribution to the science of didactics. This is an important innovation gained importance. He recommended, first of all, to connect education with children's labor. J. J. Rousseau (1712-1778) is a French philosopher-enlightener. He created a unique theory in the field of education. In his works, he expressed the idea of the need to prepare children for labor, and emphasized the importance of physical, mental and moral education in the upbringing of young people, as well as the importance of communication with nature. These ideas are considered to be among the most relevant, philosophical and educational ideas of their time.

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